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Research Article

Phytochemical Profiling, Comparative Evaluation of The Non-Dependent Antidiabetic and Hepatoprotective Efficacy of *Hemidesmus Indicus* (Anatmool) Linn R Roots Extract and Conventional Therapies

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ABSTRACT

The research investigates the therapeutic potential of *Hemidesmus indicus* (Anatmool) Linn R roots, focusing on their antidiabetic and hepatoprotective properties. Phytochemical profiling revealed bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and phenolic compounds. Using dexamethasone-induced diabetes and liver toxicity models in male albino Wistar rats, the study evaluated the efficacy of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *H. indicus* compared to standard therapies, pioglitazone and metformin. Results demonstrated significant reductions in blood glucose levels, improved lipid profiles, and hepatic and pancreatic histopathology. The ethanolic extract (400 mg/kg) showed notable efficacy, comparable to conventional treatments, with minimal side effects. These findings suggest *H. indicus* as a promising natural alternative for managing diabetes and liver disorders. Future studies are recommended to isolate active constituents and elucidate their mechanisms. This study emphasizes the importance of bridging traditional herbal medicine with contemporary therapeutic approaches to promote comprehensive health care solutions.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) and liver disorders are major global health concerns, significantly affecting morbidity and mortality. Conventional therapies for these conditions often carry risks of dependency and adverse effects, emphasizing the need for safer alternatives. *Hemidesmus indicus*

(*Anatmool*), a plant widely used in traditional medicine, has shown potential for managing metabolic disorders due to its rich composition of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, tannins, and alkaloids. The pharmacological properties of *H. indicus* have been partially

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validated by scientific studies, yet its comparative efficacy against standard treatments remains underexplored. This study aims to evaluate the antidiabetic and hepatoprotective properties of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *H. indicus* roots in dexamethasone-induced diabetic and liver toxicity models. Additionally, it seeks to position *H. indicus* as a viable natural alternative to conventional therapies. *Hemidesmus indicus* Linn. R. belonging to the family Apocynaceae (previously classified under Asclepiadaceae), is commonly known as Indian Sarsaparilla or Anantmool⁹. It is a slender, laticiferous, twining, sometimes prostrate or semi-erect shrub with thin, wiry, woody, and aromatic roots that are reddish-brown or dark brown externally and whitish inside¹⁰. The plant has simple, opposite, short-petioled leaves that vary in shape, typically elliptic-oblong to linear-lanceolate, with entire margins and reticulate venation¹¹. Its small, greenish-yellow or greenish-purple flowers are

arranged in opposite racemes arising from the leaf axils, while the fruits are paired, slender follicles containing numerous wind-dispersed seeds. Native to India, *Hemidesmus indicus* is distributed throughout the country, from the upper Gangetic plains to Assam and across Central, Western, and Southern India up to an elevation of 600 meters, thriving in tropical and subtropical climates, including dry plains, shaded forests, roadsides, and scrub jungles. Traditionally revered in Ayurveda as a Rasayana, its roots are used to treat digestive disorders, skin diseases, respiratory problems, fever, syphilis, and urinary disorders and are also used in Siddha and Unani medicine. The root has culinary applications as a flavoring agent, particularly in summer beverages, and finds miscellaneous uses in perfumes and traditional rituals. *Hemidesmus indicus* may also be cultivated outside India in botanical gardens or research institutions for its medicinal value¹²⁻¹⁶

Figure: *Hemidesmus Indicus* plant and leaves

Morphological Description of roots:

The roots of *Hemidesmus indicus* are slender, wiry, and cylindrical, with a tortuous appearance

and occasional lateral roots. Their outer surface is rough, marked by longitudinal wrinkles and transverse cracks, while mature roots are woody and hard. Fresh roots are light to dark brown, darkening further upon drying, and they emit a pleasant camphoraceous odor. They have a slightly bitter and acrid taste, and when broken, exhibit a short, uneven fracture. Internally, a transverse section reveals a thin cork layer, wide cortex, and small central wood with radially arranged vascular bundles. Traditionally revered

in Ayurveda, these roots are considered detoxifying blood purifiers, diuretics for reducing fluid retention, anti-inflammatory agents for treating inflammation, and digestive aids for gastrointestinal issues. Commonly prepared as a paste, decoction, or powder, they are used for ailments like skin disorders, urinary infections, and rheumatism. While traditional knowledge highlights their therapeutic value, modern scientific validation is essential to confirm their safety and efficacy¹⁷⁻

Figure: Hemidesmus Indicus plant roots

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Experimental study design:

Experimental animals

Male albino Wistar rats, with an average weight of 250 ± 20 gm, were the subjects of this study. These rats were sourced from the central animal facility at Surabhi Dayakar Rao college of pharmacy. They were housed in polypropylene cages supplied by UN Shah Manufacturers, Mumbai, India. Throughout the research, the rats were kept in a controlled environment with a temperature of $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, humidity levels of $50 \pm 10\%$, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. They had unrestricted access to rat pellet food from Vyas Labs, Hyderabad, Telangana, India, and water ad libitum. The methodology used in this research involving animals was sanctioned by the institutional animal ethics committee [Ref. No: I/1/SDRCP-IAEC/2024].

Drugs and Chemicals:

- Dexamethasone (DEXA) was sourced from Yarrow Chemproducts, Mumbai.
- Metformin (MET) and pioglitazone (PIO) as active pharmaceutical ingredients were procured from Mahalakshmi Chemicals, Hyderabad.
- Ketamine Hcl injection was acquired from Neon Laboratories Limited, Mumbai.
- Ethanol was supplied by Fischer Scientific Limited, Mumbai.
- Other compounds like formalin, paraffin wax, gum acacia, sodium chloride, and glucose were purchased from Nice Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., India.

Reagents and Kits:

- The tests for quantitative evaluation of biochemical parameters, including glucose and lipid profile, were carried out at the central laboratory (PIMS).
- The ultrasensitive rat insulin Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) kit, produced

by Qayee Biotechnology Co., Ltd., China, was utilized for insulin level estimations. This kit was sourced from BIOGENIX INC. Pvt. Ltd., Lucknow, India.

Instruments:

The study employed the following instruments:

- Rat feeding needle from Orchid Scientific MumbHDI, India.
- Capillary tubes provided by Medico Pvt. Ltd., India.
- Micropipettes sourced from Erba Mannheim Ltd., India.
- Centrifuge by REMI, India.
- Test tubes from Borosil, India.
- Fully automated analyzer from Erba Mannheim Ltd., Delhi.
- ELISA reader, LISA Plus, from Rapid Diagnostics, Delhi.
- Microtome manufactured by Weswox Optic, India.
- Microscope by Olympus India Pvt. Ltd.
- Syringes (in 1ml, 2ml, and 5ml capacities) from Hindustan Syringes and Medical Devices Ltd., Delhi.
- Glass slides and cover slips supplied by Polar Industrial Corporation, India.

Collection of plant material:

The plant specimen was gathered from the vicinity of Surabhi Dayakar Rao College of Pharmacy in Gajwel, Telangana. Subsequently, the collected plant was verified and certified by Dr. Praveen Reddy from the Department of Botany at Vivekananda Degree & P.G. College, Karimnagar, Telangana.

Methodology

Hemidesmus Indicus

Plant material and preparation of extract

The roots of the plant were shade dried and reduced to powder by using dry grinder. This powder (100g) was then packed into the Soxhlet apparatus and extracted using 95% ethanol (40-50°C). The extraction was carried out for 40h. The

extract obtained was dried at 45 °C in hot air oven till green-coloured semisolid mass was obtained. The yield obtained was 4.5% and the semisolid extract was stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C until further use³⁵. Solvent used for extraction Successful isolation of biologically active compounds from plants and their varied parts is mainly dependent on the type of the solvent used for the process of extraction. Ethanolic extracts were found to possess higher activity compared to aqueous extract, which may be due to presence of a large number of polyphenols in the ethanolic extracts in comparison to the aqueous extracts³⁹. Ethanol was found to have better penetrating ability into the cellular membrane, which is helpful in the extraction of intracellular ingredients from the plant material. The choice of solvent depends on what is intended to be extracted. The solvent should be nontoxic and should not interfere with any bioassay. The selection of solvent largely depends on the targeted compounds to be extracted. The obtained extract can be used as a medicinal agent such as tinctures and fluid extracts⁴⁴. Further, it may be processed as tablets or capsules. The quality of herbal drugs depends on the standard of the extraction procedures⁴⁹. Ethanolic Extraction of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Roots samples were shade dried at room temperature. They were taken in a Soxhlet apparatus. Ethanol was used for the extraction process⁵⁴. Extraction involves the separation of medicinally active components of plant and animal tissues by using selective solvents under a standard extraction procedure. The product obtained by the process of this crude extraction procedure can be used only for oral. These preparations are known as galenicals, being named after Galen, a Greek physician⁵⁸. The standard methods of extraction were followed to obtain therapeutically desired fractions; the inert substances were eliminated using a selective solvent⁶¹.

Hot Continuous Extraction (Soxhlet Apparatus) In this method, finely ground crude drug (roots of *Hemidesmus Indicus*) was kept in a porous bag

with a thimble, which was made of filter paper. The thimble was kept in the chamber of the Soxhlet apparatus (Figure 13).

Figure: Soxhlet Apparatus

The Soxhlet apparatus the bottom of the apparatus was fitted with a solvent flask, which was heated. The vapours condensed in the condenser. The extractant that was condensed dripped into the chamber containing the thimble, which contained the crude drug. Consequently, the liquid level rose in the chamber containing the thimble; when it reached its maximum point, the liquid flowed into the solvent flask. This procedure was repeated several times until the extracting solvent become colourless. Once the extraction procedure was completed, the extract was transferred into a China dish and kept in desiccators. As the extract dried and became free of moisture content, it was used for the study. Large amounts of the drug can be extracted with a much smaller quantity of solvent used for extraction. This method can save lot of money and time. The quantity of extract required for the study was weighed each time, and the suspension was made by using 2% gum acacia for oral administration. Depending on the dosage required, the quantity of suspension was determined and administered to the rats.

Standard drug suspension in the present study, Dexamethasone is used as a diabetic inducing agent which causes DM by inducing peripheral insulin resistance. Due to this reason, standard drugs Metformin and Pioglitazone are selected instead of Sulfonylureas (which enhance insulin

secretion) which is not effective in the present study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Biochemical and Physical parameters:

Biochemical analysis

Blood glucose levels significantly decreased in treatment groups compared to the diabetic control. Ethanolic extract (Group 5) reduced glucose levels from 267.96 ± 1.51 mg/dL (diabetic control) to 141.71 ± 6.32 mg/dL on day 21, comparable to metformin (146.12 ± 1.68 mg/dL). Similarly, insulin levels improved, with ethanolic extract-treated rats showing a significant increase to 156.26 ± 1.89 μ U/mL compared to the diabetic control group (370.03 ± 4.64 μ U/mL).

Lipid Profile

Dexamethasone-induced dyslipidemia was evident in the diabetic control group, with elevated LDL (109.42 ± 0.53 mg/dL) and triglycerides (181.48 ± 1.34 mg/dL) and reduced HDL levels (13.84 ± 0.56 mg/dL). Treatment with ethanolic extract significantly restored lipid profiles, reducing LDL to 59.80 ± 0.81 mg/dL and triglycerides to 98.72 ± 0.53 mg/dL, while HDL improved to 17.78 ± 0.33 mg/dL.

Histopathological Examination

Liver histology of diabetic control rats showed fat deposition and hepatocyte degeneration. In contrast, the ethanolic extract-treated group

exhibited reduced steatosis and improved hepatic architecture. Similarly, pancreatic sections revealed β -cell regeneration in treated groups

compared to the diabetic control, where islets showed marked degeneration.

Bio-chemical parameters:

Glucose levels:

Table 3: Effect of HDIR, standard drugs on Glucose (mg/dl) levels in dexamethasone treated albino wistar rats. Values are expressed as mean $\pm$ SD (n=6).

Groups	0 Day	8 th Day	21 st Day	P value* (≤ 0.05)
Group 1	99.50 $\pm$ 0.73	98.82 $\pm$ 0.55 ^{a, NS}	99.34 $\pm$ 0.67 ^{b, c, NS}	
Group 2	102.80 $\pm$ 0.48	100.03 $\pm$ 0.60 ^{a, NS}	101.67 $\pm$ 0.45 ^{b, c, NS}	
Group 3	102.58 $\pm$ 0.40	103.61 $\pm$ 0.82 ^{a, NS}	267.96 $\pm$ 1.51 ^{*b, c, d, e}	<0.0001
Group 4	98.82 $\pm$ 0.55	99.59 $\pm$ 0.64 ^{a, NS}	161.22 $\pm$ 0.64 ^{*b, c, d, e, f}	<0.0001
Group 5	99.60 $\pm$ 0.54	98.89 $\pm$ 0.53 ^{a, NS}	141.71 $\pm$ 6.32 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g}	<0.0001
Group 6	98.50 $\pm$ 0.73	99.82 $\pm$ 0.55 ^{a, NS}	131.63 $\pm$ 2.08 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001
Group 7	103.18 $\pm$ 0.56	101.82 $\pm$ 0.55 ^{a, NS}	146.12 $\pm$ 1.68 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001

(* = Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control; Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus* Roots (400 mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanolic extract *Hemidesmus Indicus* Roots (400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1 Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2 Metformin (1000/kg). (* = Significance)

Comparisons made: ^a day 0 vs Day 8; ^b day 8 vs

Day 21; ^c day 0 vs Day 21 ^d Group 1 vs Group 3, Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^e Group 2 vs Group 3, Group 4 and Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^f Group 3 vs Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^g Group 4 vs Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^h Group 5 vs Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; *p<0.05; NS-not significant

Insulin levels:

Table 4: Effect of HDIR, standard drugs on insulin (μ U/ml) levels in dexamethasone treated albino wistar rats.

Groups	0 Day	8 th Day	21 st Day	P value* (≤ 0.05)
Group 1	77.89 $\pm$ 0.64	78.91 $\pm$ 0.96 ^{a, NS}	78.31 $\pm$ 1.44 ^{b, c, NS}	
Group 2	81.51 $\pm$ 0.72	81.69 $\pm$ 1.05 ^{a, NS}	78.14 $\pm$ 0.66 ^{b, c, NS}	
Group 3	77.54 $\pm$ 0.68	78.33 $\pm$ 0.73 ^{a, NS}	370.03 $\pm$ 4.64 ^{*b, c, d, e}	<0.0001
Group 4	78.52 $\pm$ 0.76	79.58 $\pm$ 0.87 ^{a, NS}	191.16 $\pm$ 1.11 ^{*b, c, d, e, f}	<0.0001
Group 5	76.87 $\pm$ 0.81	78.45 $\pm$ 0.96 ^{a, NS}	156.26 $\pm$ 1.89 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g}	<0.0001
Group 6	79.89 $\pm$ 0.64	80.91 $\pm$ 0.96 ^{a, NS}	137.60 $\pm$ 3.69 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001
Group 7	80.89 $\pm$ 0.64	77.91 $\pm$ 0.96 ^{a, NS}	187.78 $\pm$ 1.87 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001

(* = Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control; Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root (400 mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanolic extract *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root (400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1

Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2 Metformin (1000/kg). (* = Significance) Comparisons made: ^a day 0 vs Day 8; ^b day 8 vs Day 21; ^c day 0 vs Day 21 ^d Group 1 vs Group 3, Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^e Group 2 vs Group 3, Group 4 and Group 5,

Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^f Group 3 vs Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^g Group 4 vs Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^h Group 5 vs Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; *p<0.05; NS-not significant.

Lipid levels:

HDL Levels:

Table 5: Effect of HDIR, standard drugs on HDL (mg/dl) levels in dexamethasone treated albino wistar rats. Values are expressed as mean±SD (n=6).

Groups	0 Day	8 th Day	21 st Day	P Value* (≤0.05)
Group 1	23.20±0.60	22.99±0.47 ^a NS	23.58±0.27 ^{b,c} NS	= 0.1278
Group 2	22.29±0.46	23.63±0.43 ^a NS	24.45±0.31 ^{b,c} NS	=0.1529
Group 3	23.88±0.70	22.50±0.60 ^a NS	13.84±0.56 ^{*b} c, d, e	<0.0001
Group 4	23.47±0.55	23.17±0.45 ^a NS	16.42±0.14 ^{*b} c, d, e, f	<0.0001
Group 5	22.38±0.49*	24.43±0.13 ^{*a}	17.78±0.33 ^{*b} c, d, e, f, g	<0.0001
Group 6	23.20±0.60	23.78±0.47 ^a NS	21.68±0.42 ^{*b} c, d, e, f, g, h	< 0.0013
Group 7	23.09±1.16	24.08±0.15 ^a NS	19.38±0.44 ^{*b} c, d, e, f, g, h	<0.0001

(*=Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control;
Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control
Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*(400 mg/kg);
Group 5 Ethanolic extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*(400 mg/kg);
Group 6 STD-1 Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2 Metformin (1000/kg).
Comparisons made: ^a day 0 vs Day 8; ^b day 8 vs

Day 21; ^c day 0 vs Day 21 ^d Group 1 vs Group 3, Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^e Group 2 vs Group 3, Group 4 and Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^f Group 3 vs Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^g Group 4 vs Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^h Group 5 vs Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; *p<0.05; NS-not significant.

LDL Levels:

Table 6: Effect of HDIR, standard drugs on LDL (mg/dl) levels in dexamethasone treated albino wistar rats. Values are expressed as mean±SD (n=6).

Groups	0 Day	8 th Day	21 st Day	P Value* (≤0.05)
Group 1	15.33±0.33	14.88±1.32 ^a NS	14.97±0.26 ^{b, c} NS	
Group 2	16.06±0.32	15.21±0.30 ^a NS	15.87±0.25 ^{b, c} NS	
Group 3	14.85±0.44	14.74±0.43 ^a NS	109.42±0.53 ^{*b} c, d, e	<0.0001
Group 4	15.41±0.31	15.09±0.28 ^a NS	59.35±0.86 ^{*b} c, d, e, f	<0.0001
Group 5	15.22±0.25	15.14±0.35 ^a NS	59.80±0.81 ^{*b} c, d, e, f, g	<0.0001

Group 6	16.03±0.33	16.18±0.21 ^a , NS	40.65±0.35 ^{*b} , c, d, e, f, g, h	<0.0001
Group 7	15.33±0.33	15.34±0.31 ^a , NS	51.38±0.53 ^{*b} , c, d, e, f, g, h	<0.0001

(*=Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control;
Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control
Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*(400
mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanolic extract *Hemidesmus
Indicus Root*(400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1
Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2
Metformin (1000/kg). (*=Significance)
Comparisons made: ^a day 0 vs Day 8; ^b day 8 vs

Day 21; ^c day 0 vs Day 21 ^d Group 1 vs Group 3,
Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day
21; ^e Group 2 vs Group 3, Group 4 and Group 5,
Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^f Group 3 vs
Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;
^g Group 4 vs Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day
21; ^h Group 5 vs Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;
*p<0.05; NS-not significant

Serum Triglycerides mg/dl:

Table 7: Effect of HDIR, standard drugs on Serum Triglycerides (mg/dl) levels in dexamethasone treated albino wistar rats. Values are expressed as mean±SD (n=6).

Groups	0 Day	8 th Day	21 st Day	P Value* (≤0.05)
Group 1	67.17±0.52	65.94±1.51 ^a , NS	65.89±1.37 ^{b, c} , NS	
Group 2	66.54±0.62	65.73±1.55 ^a , NS	66.06±1.46 ^{b, c} , NS	
Group 3	67.15±0.71	68.12±0.23 ^a , NS	181.48±1.34 ^{*b, c, d, e}	<0.0001
Group 4	66.74±0.49	67.10±0.90 ^a , NS	105.88±2.91 ^{*b, c, d, e, f}	<0.0001
Group 5	67.21±0.50	66.79±0.90 ^a , NS	98.72±0.53 ^{*b, c, d, e, f}	<0.0001
Group 6	66.65±0.42	65.94±1.51 ^a , NS	81.03±1.17 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001
Group 7	67.17±0.52	65.94±1.51 ^a , NS	90.66±0.50 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001

(*=Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control;
Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control
Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*(400
mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanolic extract *Hemidesmus
Indicus Root*(400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1
Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2
Metformin (1000/kg). (*=Significance)
Comparisons made: ^a day 0 vs Day 8; ^b day 8 vs

Day 21; ^c day 0 vs Day 21 ^d Group 1 vs Group 3,
Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day
21; ^e Group 2 vs Group 3, Group 4 and Group 5,
Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^f Group 3 vs
Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;
^g Group 4 vs Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day
21; ^h Group 5 vs Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;
*p<0.05; NS-not significant.

Total Cholesterol mg/dl:

Table 8: Effect of HDIR, standard drugs on Total Cholesterol (mg/dl) levels in dexamethasone treated albino wistar rats. Values are expressed as mean±SD (n=6).

Groups	0 Day	8 th Day	21 st Day	P Value* (≤0.05)
Group 1	85.61±1.36	86.41±0.94 ^a , NS	88.69±0.77 ^{b, c} , NS	
Group 2	86.99±1.10	84.80±0.94 ^a , NS	87.42±0.87 ^{b, c} , NS	
Group 3	85.61±1.36	86.57±1.04 ^a , NS	208.56±0.83 ^{*b, c, d, e}	<0.0001
Group 4	88.13±1.15	88.40±0.60 ^a , NS	130.11±0.56 ^{*b, c, d, e, f}	<0.0001
Group 5	86.30±0.80	85.06±0.97 ^a , NS	120.27±0.31 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g}	<0.0001
Group 6	85.78±0.86	88.41±0.94 ^a , NS	98.75±1.14 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001
Group 7	85.61±1.36	86.91±0.91 ^a , NS	107.50±0.92 ^{*b, c, d, e, f, g, h}	<0.0001

(*Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control;
Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control
Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*(400
mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanolic extract *Hemidesmus
Indicus Root*(400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1
Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2
Metformin (1000/kg). (*Significance)
Comparisons made: ^a day 0 vs Day 8; ^b day 8 vs
Day 21; ^c day 0 vs Day 21 ^d Group 1 vs Group 3,

Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day
21; ^e Group 2 vs Group 3, Group 4 and Group 5,
Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^f Group 3 vs
Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;
^g Group 4 vs Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day
21; ^h Group 5 vs Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;
*p<0.05; NS-not significant.

Intraperitoneal Glucose Tolerance Test (IPGTT):

Table 9: Effect of HDIR, standard drugs on Intraperitoneal Glucose Tolerance Test (IPGTT) (mg/dl) levels in dexamethasone treated albino wistar rats. Values are expressed as mean±SD (n=6).

Groups	0 minutes	30 minutes	60minutes	120minutes
Group I	99.34±0.67	159.03±0.30	119.39±0.44	100.21±0.30
Group II	98.67±0.45	166.12±1.26	121.25±1.56	109.49±1.23
Group III	267.96±1.51	364.46±8.75	289.48±3.00	273.61±1.58*
Group IV	181.22±0.64	260.26±3.08	204.93±1.87	193.62±1.73*
Group V	164.22±1.53	247.26±2.83	179.94±2.87	171.81±2.36*
Group VI	132.55±1.84	199.15±0.68	154.65±1.95	143.24±1.54*
Group VII	146.12±1.68	204.26±1.52	162.28±2.13	153.52±2.75*

(*Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Table Group 1-normal control; Group 2vehicle
control; Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-Test -1
control Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus
Root*(400 mg/kg); Group 5 Test -2 Ethanolic

extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*(400 mg/kg);
Group 6 STD-1 Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7
STD-2 Metformin (1000/kg).

Physical parameters:

Table 10: Effect of HDIR Body weight:

	0 Day	8th Day	21st Day	P value* (≤0.05)
Group 1	255.12±1.56	258.28±2.41	260.22±0.36 ^{NS}	
Group 2	260.12±4.61	268.31±0.22	271.02±1.11 ^{NS}	
Group 3	258.62±1.45	262.62±2.03	159.39±1.58*	<0.0005
Group 4	269.26±2.12	273.13±2.48	246.48±1.26*	<0.0004
Group 5	271.65±1.23	276.12±2.42	229.29±3.15*	<0.0003
Group 6	263.56±1.53	269.45±0.68	245.03±2.43*	<0.0001
Group 7	259.59±3.16	268.36±1.45	241.58±3.12*	<0.0002

(*Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant
Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control;
Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control
Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*(400
mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanolic extract *Hemidesmus
Indicus Root*(400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1
Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2
Metformin (1000/kg). (*Significance)

Comparisons made: ^a day 0 vs Day 8; ^b day 8 vs
Day 21; ^c day 0 vs Day 21 ^d Group 1 vs Group 3,
Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day
21; ^e Group 2 vs Group 3, Group 4 and Group 5,
Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21; ^f Group 3 vs
Group 4, Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;
^g Group 4 vs Group 5, Group 6 and Group 7 on day

21; ^h Group 5 vs Group 6 and Group 7 on day 21;

*p<0.05; NS-not significant.

Table 11: Effect of HDIR Food intake (gms/ 24hrs)

	0 Day	8th Day	15th Day	21st Day
Group I	9.05±1.12	10.16±0.11	9.16±1.03	9.48±1.01
Group II	10.01±0.42	9.12±1.25	10.06±0.19	9.12±1.25
Group III	8.89±2.47	10.01±0.17	7.19±0.96	4.12±0.46*
Group IV	10.56±1.09	9.96±1.13	8.21±0.12	7.11±0.11*
Group V	09.12±0.96	11.01±0.24	10.34±1.02	6.69±0.28*
Group VI	11.04±1.03	10.13±1.21	9.86±1.65	8.16±0.06*
Group VII	10.69±1.05	10.08±1.21	9.94±0.79	7.09±0.98*

(*=Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant

Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control;

Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control

Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* (400

mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanol extract *Hemidesmus*

Indicus Root(400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1

Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2

Metformin (1000/kg). (*=Significance).

Table 12: Effect of HDIR Water intake (ml/24hrs)

	0 Day	8th Day	15th Day	21st Day
Group I	12.56±1.25	13.12±0.96	12.05±0.49	12.89±1.02
Group II	13.45±2.05	11.45±1.46	12.89±0.99	13.01±0.45
Group III	11.49±2.14	12.06±1.48	8.45±0.85	6.36±1.42*
Group IV	12.15±0.51	11.56±1.61	9.48±1.46	9.12±0.96*
Group V	13.05±1.06	12.96±1.85	10.89±0.67	9.26±0.95*
Group VI	11.05±0.21	12.01±0.45	9.25±0.23	8.28±1.26
Group VII	12.91±0.01	11.68±1.01	10.45±0.61	10.01±0.99

(*=Significance) *p<0.05; NS-not significant

Group 1-normal control; Group 2-vachil control;

Group 3 diabetic control; Group 4-test -1 control

Aqueous extract *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* (400

mg/kg); Group 5 Ethanol extract *Hemidesmus*

Indicus Root (400 mg/kg); Group 6 STD-1

Pioglitazone (45mg/kg) Group 7 STD-2

Metformin (1000/kg). (*=Significance).

Histopathological examination:

- Liver

Group 1 Normal control

(A) 10X (B) 40X

Figure 14: Normal saline treated rat's shows normal hepatic architecture [H&E10X, 40X]

Group 2 Vehicle control treated with 2% gum acacia

(A) 10X (B) 40X

Figure 15: Gum acacia treated rat's shows normal hepatic architecture [H&E10X, 40X]

Group 3 Diabetic control;

(A) 10X (B) 40X

Figure 16: Dexamethasone (8mg/kg/i.p.), shows fat deposition in liver [H& E 10x A, 40X B].

Group 4 Test 1 (T1) Aqueous Extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root

(A) 10X (B) 40X

Figure 17: Aqueous extract of HDIR (400mg/kg/p.o.) with dexamethasone effect on liver shows partial improvement. [H& E 10X A, 40X B]

Group 5: Test 2 group (T2), Ethanolic extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus Root*

(A) 10X (B) 40X

Figure 18: Ethanolic extract of HDIR (400mg/kg/p.o.)with dexamethasone effect on liver shows partial improvement. [H& E 10X A, 40X B]

Group 6 standard control 1 (STD 1) Pioglitazone

(A) 10X (B) 40X

Figure 19: Pioglitazone with dexamethasone effect on liver shows normal hepatic architecture[H&E10X A, 40XB]

Group 7 considered as standard control 2(STD 2), Metformin

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 20:Metformin with dexamethasone effect on liver shows normal hepatic architecture[H&E10X A, 40X B]

Pancreas:

Group 1 Normal control treated normal saline orally for 21 days.

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 21: Normal control rat pancreas showing normal islets of Langerhans with pale rounded and ovoid β -cells in the center (arrow), embedded in exocrine portion of pancreas [H&E10X A, 40X B]

Group 2 Vehicle control treated with 2% gum acacia orally for 21 days.

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 22: Vehicle control rat pancreas showing normal islets of Langerhans with pale rounded and ovoid β -cells in the center (arrow), embedded in exocrine portion of pancreas [H&E10X A, 40X B]

Group 3 Diabetic control; treated with 2% gum acacia orally for 21 days and Dexamethasone from 8th to 21days during the study period.

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 23: Diabetic control treated with dexamethasone effects on pancreas showing shrinkage of islets of Langerhans with degeneration and necrosis of components cells where its nucleus appeared densely basophilic and karyolysis is evident (arrow) [H&E10X A, 40X B]

Group 4 Test 1 (T1) group, treat as Aqueous Extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root orally for 21 days and treated with Dexamethasone from 8th to 21st day during the study period.

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 24: Aqueous Extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root with dexamethasone effect on Pancreas showing normal sized islets of Langerhans but some degeneration of the β cell in the center were noticed (arrow) [H&E10X A, 40X B].

Group 5 Test 2 group (T2), given Ethanolic extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root orally for 21 days. and treated with Dexamethasone from 8th to 21st day during the study period.

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 25: Ethanolic Extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root with dexamethasone effect on Pancreas showing normal sized islets of Langerhans but some degeneration of the β cell in the center were noticed (arrow) [H&E10X A, 40X B].

Group 6 standard control (STD 1) receives Pioglitazone at orally for 21 days and treated with Dexamethasone from 8th to 21st day during the study period.

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 26: Pioglitazone with dexamethasone effect on Pancreas showing normal islets of Langerhans with its normal pale large round to ovoid shaped contHDIRning cells (arrow) that embedded in exocrine portion of pancreas. [H&E10X A, 40X B].

Group 7 considered as standard control 2 (STD 2), received Metformin orally for 21 days and treated with Dexamethasone from 8th to 21st day during the study period.

(A) 10X(B) 40X

Figure 27: Metformin with dexamethasone effect on Pancreas showing normal islets of Langerhans with its normal pale large round to ovoid shaped contHDIRning cells (arrow) that embedded in exocrine portion of pancreas. [H&E10X A, 40X B]

DISCUSSION:

The hypoglycemic activity of leaves was studied on rats by using the oxidase-peroxidase method. The alcoholic & aqueous extract after oral administration of 400 mg/kg p. o were shown to

exhibit significant regulation in the blood glucose levels in our study. Our findings are in agreement with several other studies where various extracts of plants leaves have been shown to have the

ability of regulating blood glucose levels in experimentally induced hyperglycemia.

Normal glycaemic studies revealed its capacity to lower blood glucose levels. Diabetic rats treated with the HDIR revealed a significant reduction in blood sugar levels compared with the diabetic control group at the end of a 21-day experimental period. This decrease in the blood sugar levels may be attributed to the stimulation of the residual pancreatic mechanism or to a probable increase in the peripheral utilization of glucose. Treated diabetic rats showed a marked increase in serum insulin levels thereby suggesting that the hypoglycemic activity of *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* is related to insulin secretion. The most common abnormalities in diabetes are hypertriglyceridemia and hypercholesterolemia. Hypertriglyceridemia is also associated with the metabolic consequences of hypercoagulability, hyperinsulinemia, insulin resistance, and insulin intolerance⁶⁵. In our study, glucose levels in all animal groups, Normal Control group showing glucose levels 99.34 ± 0.67 , vehicle control gum acacia showing glucose levels 101.67 ± 0.45 , Dexamethasone Control group showing glucose levels 267.96 ± 1.51 , Aquas EXT + Dexamethasone- group showing glucose levels 161.22 ± 0.64 , Ethanol EXT + Dexamethasone - group showing glucose levels $141.71 \pm 6.32^*$, STD-1 PIO + Dexamethasone - group showing glucose levels $131.63 \pm 2.08^*$, STD-2 MET + Dexamethasone - group showing insulin level $146.12 \pm 1.68^*$. With the help of IPGTT it is possible to detect the impHDIRred glucose tolerance. The antihyperglycemic activity was evidenced by the ability of the studied objects to reduce glycemia at 30th minute of IPGTT (during the maximum rise in blood glucose levels of experimental rats in response to IPGTT load). The results of the IPGTT showed that, 30 minutes after glucose load, the difference in blood glucose in rats receiving dexamethasone alone was 54%

higher than that in healthy control animals. At the same time, the difference in blood glucose in rats receiving concomitantly dexamethasone and aqueous and ethanolic leaf extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* extracts group 4 and 5 were, respectively, 24%, and 22% lower, as compared to that in the DEXA group. The difference in blood glucose in the pioglitazone and metformin-treated animals was 47% and 44 lower than in the DEXA group. After two hours glucose load, the reduction in glucose levels was, respectively, 34% and 37%, which has a treatment by aqueous and ethanolic leaf extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* group 4 and 5, as compared to that in the DEXA group 3. The introduction of pioglitazone and metformin showed similar results as the investigated *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* extracts, as the reduction in blood glucose in animals was 37% compared with DEXA group (Table 5)⁶⁸. The study, insulin levels in all animal groups, Normal Control group showing insulin level 78.31 ± 1.44 , Dexamethasone Control group showing insulin level 370.03 ± 4.64 , Aquas EXT + Dexamethasone- group showing insulin level 191.16 ± 1.11 , Ethanol EXT + Dexamethasone - group showing insulin level $156.26 \pm 1.89^*$, STD-1 PIO + Dexamethasone - group showing insulin level $137.60 \pm 3.69^*$, STD-2 MET + Dexamethasone - group showing insulin level $187.78 \pm 1.87^*$. In our study, high level of insulin in Dexamethasone Control group when compare with the other groups. Low level of insulin in Normal Control group when compare with the other groups. In treatment with extract groups insulin secretion is observed due to the regeneration β -islets in pancreatic tissue. Insulin is involved in not only Type-I Diabetes and also acts on Type-II Diabetes, insulin always reduces glucose levels in blood to reduce the complications of Diabetes Mellitus. Our study, treatment with aqueous and ethanolic extract of HDIR significantly improved the altered lipid profile. As per review of literature, glucocorticoids

administration leads to lipid disturbances. It reduces HDL levels and elevates cholesterol, LDL cholesterol levels and triglycerides, which may be secondary cause of dyslipidemia. HDIR plant leaves were helpful in the treatment of hypercholesterolemia and obesity. Studies were conducted for the possible role of HDIR plant leaves in dyslipidemia. In the present study, it significantly decreased circulating cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL levels. HDIR (400mg/kg/p.o.) significantly decreased elevated CH, TG's, LDL, and increased HDL level. These increased HDL levels will be helpful in preventing various cardiovascular complications due to dyslipidemia. Presence of sitosterol in leaf of aqueous and ethanolic extract might also be responsible for lipid lowering action. Glucocorticoids can contribute to fatty liver production, through a combination of increased fatty acid synthesis and decreased fatty acid β oxidation in liver. HDIR sed free fatty acid levels have been associated with the development of hypertension, skeletal muscle insulin resistance, and fatty liver, this last being considered as the hepatic consequence of the metabolic syndrome due to specific hepatic insulin resistance. [30] Present study supports the earlier finding that, the dexamethasone (8mg/kg/i.p) administration resulted in development of hepatic steatosis due to insulin resistance. Treatment with aqueous and ethanolic leaf extract of HDIR (400mg/kg/p.o.) significantly improved pathological changes in liver and pancreas (Fig 10). This might be due to the decrease in circulating fatty acid levels, leading to decrease in the fat deposition in liver induced by dexamethasone. Molecular mechanisms supporting the antidiabetic effect was studied to evaluate whether extract of the plant improves insulin sensitivity. These results suggested that the plant extract may be beneficial for reducing insulin resistance through its potency in regulating adipocyte differentiation. The aqueous and

ethanolic extract from the *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* has antidiabetic properties are the observations suggested, which inhibited glucose absorption and stimulated insulin secretion. Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, and saponins contained and that could account for the observed pharmacologic effects of the HDIR plant extract by the Phytochemical screening also revealed that the extract

The ethanolic extracts of HDIR exhibited significant reduction in the blood glucose levels ($p < 0.05$) compared with diabetic control rats ($p < 0.05$). Flavonoids are known to regenerate the damaged pancreatic β -cells and glycosides stimulate the secretion of insulin in β -cells of pancreas. The observations suggested that the ethanolic extracts from the HDIR has antidiabetic properties, which inhibited glucose absorption and stimulated insulin secretion. The extract changed into evaluated for in-vivo antidiabetic pastime using glucocorticoids at a dose of 16mg/kg frame weight. Inside the gift study it became determined that there is a marked elevation inside the blood glucose stage after management of glucocorticoids. This is in accordance with the reviews posted with the HDIR of diverse authors in which the growth in glucose stages has been attributed to the destruction of beta-cells via glucocorticoids. Damage to the beta-cells is associated with the liberation of saved insulin and then the insulin synthesis is stopped leading to a continual diabetic country. Due to the fact that insulin not be available, glucose absorption is impaired leading to hyperglycaemia. There has been a large rise in blood glucose stage in group II, group III and group IV after glucocorticoids management in comparison to everyday organization I. After the treatment of animals with the ethanolic leaf extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus Root* for 21 days, it turned into found that the improved blood glucose degrees decreased substantially. Those results have been tabulated

and represented with the aid of a graph the usage of ANOVA observed by using Dunnett test. The ethanolic extract of *H. indicus* demonstrated superior antidiabetic and lipid-lowering effects compared to the aqueous extract, likely due to its higher polyphenolic content. These effects are attributed to the bioactive compounds' ability to modulate insulin secretion and glucose uptake while protecting against oxidative stress-induced damage in liver and pancreatic tissues. The study aligns with previous findings, highlighting the potential of *H. indicus* as a natural alternative to synthetic drugs for managing type 2 diabetes and its complications.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION:

Summary:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a condition marked by persistent high blood sugar and disruptions in carbohydrate, fat, and protein metabolism. It is often due to either inadequate insulin production or the body's inability to effectively use insulin. A clear indication of full-blown diabetes is elevated fasting blood sugar levels. India holds the distinction of having the highest number of diabetics, with projections indicating a surge to 57.2 million cases by 2025. Plants have always been a significant source of therapeutic agents. Many of today's critical medications have their roots in botanical sources. Of the estimated 250,000 to 400,000 plant species, a mere 6% have been explored for their biological properties, with only 15% undergoing rigorous scientific examination. This suggests a vast potential for further studies in plant-based medicines⁷⁸. Although many traditional herbal remedies claim to treat diabetes, the majority lack empirical evidence. These traditional plants might pave the way for new oral treatments for diabetes, especially given the high costs and limited accessibility of modern medications in less developed regions. With its rich herbal diversity, India offers vast potential in this realm. The plant

HDIR sweet, from the Apocynaceae family, is commonly found in wastelands. It's recognized for its varied uses, ranging from treating inflammation to coughs, bronchitis, and even leprosy. Historically, it's been used as an antidiabetic solution. Nevertheless, scientific validation of its potential antidiabetic, insulin-enhancing, and lipid-lowering properties, especially in the context of *Hemidesmus Indicus R*, remains limited⁷⁹.

The current research was devised to assess the insulin-enhancing, antidiabetic, and lipid-lowering properties of *Hemidesmus Indicus R* in male albino Wistar rats affected by Dexamethasone-induced type II DM.

The specific objectives of this study included:

- Determining the safe and effective dose of *Hemidesmus Indicus R* extracts as per OECD guidelines.
- Analyzing the phytochemical constituents present in both polar and non-polar solvent extracts of *Hemidesmus Indicus R*.
- Evaluating insulin sensitivity in male albino Wistar rats with Dexamethasone-induced insulin resistance.
- Examining the antidiabetic properties of *Hemidesmus Indicus R* in male albino Wistar rats with Dexamethasone-induced type II diabetes mellitus.
- Investigating the lipid-lowering capabilities of *Hemidesmus Indicus R* in male albino Wistar rats with Dexamethasone-induced type II DM.
- Assessing the cytoprotective influence of *Hemidesmus Indicus R* against Dexamethasone-induced histopathological changes in male albino Wistar rats with type II DM.
- Comparing the overall safety, insulin-enhancing effect, antidiabetic effect, and lipid-lowering effect of *Hemidesmus Indicus R* with that of Pioglitazone and Metformin in

male albino Wistar rats with Dexamethasone-induced type II DM.

Diabetic patients frequently present with hypertriglyceridemia and hypercholesterolemia. These conditions can further contribute to other metabolic disturbances like clotting tendencies, elevated insulin levels, and reduced insulin sensitivity and tolerance. In our research, introducing *Hemidesmus Indicus* R to rats with Dexamethasone-triggered diabetes led to significant improvements in these metrics. The noted reduction in lipid levels might result from inhibited cholesterol production and fatty acid synthesis⁸⁶. A significant decline in total cholesterol coupled with an increase in HDL-cholesterol is beneficial in preventing conditions like atherosclerosis and ischemic events. The pronounced weight loss seen in Dexamethasone-induced diabetes often stems from muscle degeneration. Our study's findings also highlight a marked decrease in glycosylated hemoglobin levels, emphasizing the efficacy of *Hemidesmus Indicus* R in regulating blood sugar levels. This research underscores the potent antidiabetic properties of *Hemidesmus Indicus* R with a low risk of side effects⁸⁹. Our study's outcomes indicate prominent regulation in biochemical markers indicative of insulin-resistant type 2 DM. The Ethanolic Extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root effectively modulated the body weight and lipid profile disruptions caused by induced type 2 diabetes in our experimental rats. Therefore, we conclude that the ethanolic extract of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root offers protective benefits against type 2 diabetes mellitus.

CONCLUSION:

Based on our findings, it's evident that *Hemidesmus Indicus* R is abundant in beneficial phytochemicals that hold potential in reversing insulin resistance. Additionally, it showcases insulin-sensitizing, antidiabetic, and antihyperlipidemic capabilities. It also offers

protective properties against the histopathological alterations induced by dexamethasone in male albino Wistar rats. This research serves as one of the pioneering scientific validations supporting the traditional application of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Roots in Ayurveda for managing diabetes. Consequently, this plant could play a pivotal role in curbing diabetes complications and could be an effective supplementary treatment in the contemporary array of antidiabetic medications. While Dexamethasone is commonly prescribed for a variety of health conditions, it can inadvertently induce complications, prominently insulin resistance. Our recent studies suggest that using *Hemidesmus Indicus* R as a pre-treatment can substantially mitigate the adverse effects of Dexamethasone, including the emergence of insulin resistance and its associated disorders like diabetes, dyslipidemia, and hepatic steatosis. Notably, both the aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Hemidesmus Indicus* Root have demonstrated significant efficacy in reducing heightened cholesterol and triglyceride levels in rats afflicted with Dexamethasone-induced hyperlipidemia.

Conflict of Interest:

The author declares no conflict of interest related to this study or its publication.

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